

Dissemination of results

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Lead beneficiary	RIVM	
Responsible authors	Irene van Kamp	
E-mail / phone responsible authors	Irene van Kamp (RIVM)	+31 62 111 2691
Co-authors	Kim van Wijk	Kim.van.wijk@rivm.nl
	Peter van den Hazel (INCHES)	pvdhazel@upcmail.nl
	Sonja Jeram	Sonja.Jeram@nijz.si
Reviewers	All PI's	

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1 Summary

This report contains an overall plan for communication and dissemination of the results of Equal-Life (*Chapter 2*) and the assessment of the information needs of relevant stakeholders (drafted in collaboration with WP8) (*Chapter 3*). A short summary of the development of a virtual tool box within the project and in the EHEN context is provided (*Chapter 4*). In *Chapter 5* we provide examples of dissemination activities, including a list of peer reviewed publications and conference papers thus far. Part of this text was included in D10.2. For the former, we also refer to D11.1 Communication and Dissemination Strategy (2020) of the European Human Exposome Network. Ethical issues associated with Equal-Life are not included in this report, but were discussed in detail elsewhere (D12.1 and D12.5). The scientific publication plan and rules for authorship have been described in D10.2, a living and confidential document which is updated on a regular basis.

2 Communication and dissemination of the results of Equal-Life

Effective use of project results is of great importance. In this chapter, the overall communication and dissemination of the results of Equal-Life is discussed. Existing networks will be used for interaction and knowledge exchange, thus leveraging the impact of the project. For more information we also refer to D11.1 Communication and Dissemination Strategy (2020) of the European Human Exposome Network and Deliverable 8.1.

WP10 in Equal-Life is dedicated to the promotion of the project and disseminating its results, WP9 to implementation of the tools and training sessions at the local level and the development of a Guidance document to assist users of the tool. WP8 (stakeholder involvement) also plays a key part in the effective dissemination of results. Next to the above described assessment of stakeholders' information needs, WP8 has the task to identify and involve relevant stakeholders in the development of interventions and the co-design of the Equal-Life tool. Stakeholders bring in examples of good practices which can be included in the tools. In WP9 the explicit aim is, next to technical issues, to engage the end-users in the development of the tools by co-design and providing good practices. To this end, WP9 will provide training to local stakeholders and the maintenance issues will be taken on board during the design phase. Embedding the tools in existing local tools with support of national public health institutes is one of the options worthwhile exploring.

2.1.1 Dissemination and exploitation of results outside the consortium

Impact of expected results relies heavily on the dissemination strategy. The results of Equal-Life actions and activities are being and will be disseminated within the wider scientific community, and a full range of potential users and uses including public health, environmental, policy making, setting standards, skills and training. A dissemination strategy is being developed and actualized in WP10 to reflect the objectives of the project. The aim is to be as inclusive as possible and to explain the aims and the significance of the activities to a large audience.

The Equal-Life network will use a number of existing dissemination resources, tools and infrastructures (both online and offline) which will provide information and ensure increased awareness of this project to global audiences (see communication section below). Special attention is given to equity of access to relevant scientific evidence, in that the needs of low intensity research countries and subgroups will be closely considered. The international advisors and local health services can play an

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important role in this. The liaison with the Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions, the Municipal Health Service Amsterdam (co- chair of the advisory board) - and the link with the partner from TU Delft (WP5 leader) and the Municipality of Utrecht allow for a more practical application of the Equal-Life findings in an Urban setting and will enhance the usability of the data, tools, algorithms and methods derived in the project and is settled by an in-kind contribution of the Municipal health service in Amsterdam. The dissemination activities are coordinated by a communication strategy consisting of four components. These components are listed below.

2.1.2 Dissemination of project results within the consortium

The main outputs of Equal-Life will be a set of guiding questions and mechanisms, a description of the internal and external exposome relevant for mental health and cognitive development of children, insight in the mental health and cognitive effects of environmental factors, as set of potential interventions, good practices, mapping methods, exposure modelling methods, statistical methods and algorithms, and multimodal data on physical and social exposures for at least 8 cities/countries. These tools and guidance documents will be part of a public tool. Equal-Life supports the principle of open access to the published output of research as a fundamental part of its goals since that is an effective way to provide access to the results and awareness of the tools to be used for further research as well as planning purposes. To achieve successful project execution and optimal promotion of the project objectives, strategy, and the impact of its findings is crucial. To achieve this aim, a series of communication activities is undertaken during the lifetime of the project and beyond. These activities will be tailored to the targeted audience and are described below. In addition to those targeted communications, Equal-Life will develop communication that is open to the general public. The aim here is to be as inclusive as possible and to explain the aims and the significance of the activities to a large audience. Professional communication specialist knowledgeable in the field of environment and health will support the development of this plan. The reports/guidelines and agenda will be made available outside Equal- Life through meetings and various media support. For the communication of results, different stakeholders/target groups have been identified. 1) Project partners and participants, 2) Researchers and Academics, 3) the stakeholders Community, 4) the (exposome Hubs 5) the general Public. Any dissemination activities and publications in the project, including the project website will (i) specify that the project has received Community research funding and (ii) display the European emblem. When displayed in association with a logo, the European emblem will be given appropriate prominence. To optimise communication towards different target groups, Equal-Life teams up with a Global network on Children and environmental health (INCHES) – which is linked to the WHO. Also there are strong links and agreements with the national Exposome hub and the HBM4EU national hubs, and several other NGO's in the domain of environmental and mental health and cognitive development in children. Categories of potential end-users of the Equal-Life tools can be subdivided into private, public and research sector. (see table 1)

Table 1: Overview of potential stakeholders

Private sector
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environment: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ city planners, architects, landscapers, traffic planners, traffic consultants, noise consultants/acousticians, experts for air pollution... ○ housing associations, building societies ○ NGOs for environmental issues (Greenpeace, etc., or more local associations)

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○ Tourism business, leisure industry, sports
○ CCI: Chamber of Commerce and Industry (healthy environment as a selling factor for job recruitment and/or local economy)
● Children's health, cognition
○ Physicians, health consultants, NGOs for child health/protection
○ Health insurance companies
○ Child care organisations, child health institutions
○ educational consultants/experts
○ social/welfare workers, psychologists (educational psychologists, child therapists)
○ CCI: Chamber of Commerce and Industry (child's health as a selling factor for job recruitment and/or local economy)
Research sector
● Children's health, cognition, and social issues:
○ Medical scientists: physical/mental health
○ Psychological scientists: mental health cognition (e.g. child/developmental or clinical psychologists)
○ Educators/teachers: cognition, mental health
● Environment
○ City/urban, land-use planning
○ Traffic science
○ Environmental psychology
○ Environmental epidemiology
○ Environmental science: noise impact, air pollution
○ Tourism/leisure/sports science
Public sector
● Environmental authorities:
○ local, regional, national, EU (e.g. EEA) authorities for environmental issues
○ local, regional, national, EU (authorities for transportation issues)
○ local, regional, national, EU authorities for land-use planning
○ City networks (WHO Healthy Cities Network)
○ Cities, municipalities: Environmental, transportation departments
● Health, cognition, social:
○ Supra-national authorities (EC, UNICEF, WHO)
○ City networks (WHO Healthy Cities Network)
○ Cities, municipalities: Health, family, social, school departments

Since 2023 RIVM joins the expertise network on depression of the Joint Research centre in ISPRA.

In April 2023 the JRC organised a 2-day scientific expert workshop entitled 'Crowdsourcing knowledge on depression mechanisms: From risk factors to treatment'. The workshop was designed to crowdsource transdisciplinary mechanistic scientific knowledge on depression, create a network of high-level experts, and respond to existing policy needs. The workshop featured various presentations from COM (JRC, SANTE, RTD, HADEA) and top international experts (including OECD and academia).

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In follow up we are collaborating in preparing a publication on this event. https://www.linkedin.com/posts/sandra-coecke-00b68542_transdisciplinary-transdimensional-ecjrc-activity-7051254375515627521-7Oio/?originalSubdomain=tz

2.1.3 Tools and media that will be used in communication and result dissemination

Scientific manuscripts: International and national scientific publications

Website: The Equal-Life project website provides (i) a first point of access for all the participants interested in the topics addressed by the project and (ii) extend awareness of the results at the broadest possible international scale. It will be maintained throughout the course of the project and targeted at both lay and other relevant audiences. The website also includes links to social media. A specific Equal-Life logo and graphical summary of Equal-Life was created early in the project and will enhance the projects identity and high visibility. The Equal-Life website (www.equal-life.eu) links to websites of the partner institutions (translated), the website of the European Human Exposome Network (<https://www.humanexposome.eu/>) and possibly professional websites of international organisations (WHO, OECD). All communication supports will be downloadable from the site (press releases, publishable executive summaries, projects abstracts, posters and publications, electronic newsletters, etc.).

Social media: Equal-Life has a (formerly) twitter account (@EquallifeEU) as well as a group on LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8968730/>) to inform stakeholders of the projects' process.

Briefings: Results of Equal-Life are being communicated by means of face-to-face presentations and reviews of findings and results to different levels of stakeholders and representative organizations across Europe. The public part of the Equal-Life website informs the public about key developments and key results, events, and related activities. One output of the Equal-Life work will an inventory of the major stakeholders in environment and Health in the EU including large research initiatives and centres, NGOs, policy related organs and centres at both the national and international levels and develop a searchable web-based database.

Conferences & workshops: Beyond the stakeholder events embedded in WP8, our dissemination strategy also seeks maximum exposure for the project findings at high profile conferences, seminars and workshops. These events are being used for dissemination of the project. In addition targeted

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webinars are foreseen on year 5 of the project for specific stakeholders. In 2025 an end event is planned for stakeholders possibly in collaboration with the JRC and the Athlete project of ISGlobal.

Networking and outreach to other related projects. We will be happy to share our results with other FP7 or H2020 projects. Potential common events can be envisaged to share respective expertise and gain new insights. Cross-linking of project web sites can also increase our web link popularity and page rank.

Press releases were written for the kick-off meeting and communicated at national level to newspapers and to communication offices of the participants' institutions but also at European level through the EC communication services. Any other general communication on the project is encouraged within the consortium, particularly through internet, video support and social networks in line with the Equal-Life communication strategy. Information will be processed according to the general rules on dissemination set out through the consortium agreement. Participants planning dissemination shall inform the consortium in order to get approval. The Project Management Team will make sure that financial support by the EC is highlighted on every communication support.

Public outreach aimed at specific target groups such as children, policymakers, specific stakeholder groups such as animation for all age groups popular summaries of the project and a Delphi survey.

Tools and training aimed at regional stakeholders to inform about the results, in particular urban planners.

3 Information needs Equal-Life's stakeholders

WP8 collected in the past four years information from stakeholders in order to interpret and apply the research results in policy, practice, and programmes, both at (inter)national and local level. This ensures that the generated knowledge (on exposome, mechanisms, and health effects) in Equal-Life is developed in line with the needs of the broader society, and that knowledge of the involved (public and private) stakeholders will help to interpret the results. To this end, at an early stage in the project, the research questions of Equal-Life partners are compared with the questions of relevant stakeholders and end-users (stakeholder involvement). Instead of mixing these groups, it was decided to perform these consultations in a stepwise manner.

3.1 Methods of stakeholder involvement

Three main methods of stakeholder involvement were thus far used: a Delphi survey, co-creation workshops and focus groups.

3.1.1 Delphi survey

Using the Delphi Survey method in Task 8.1 (Connecting science to policy), a bi-directional dialogue is initiated between the Equal-Life project and (inter)national stakeholders in order to 1) translate project results into effective children health policies and 2) inject knowledge about best practices and health policies into the project. The Delphi method is a structured communication technique or method, originally developed as a systematic, interactive forecasting method which relies on a panel of experts. The Delphi method is based on the assumption that group judgments are more valid than individual judgments. Participants usually answer questionnaires in two or more rounds. In Equal-Life,

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stakeholders will be asked for their input in three consecutive rounds (see Section 3.1.1.). The results of the Delphi survey sent out to stakeholders shows the information needs of the stakeholders and were linked to the results of the scientific members of the consortium. The stakeholder consultations and internal expert discussions took place also within two sets of Delphi consultations with three rounds: internal and external. The 'internal' Delphi aimed to harvest ideas and generate early discussion and inputs from Equal-Life researchers and advisory committee for the topics of interest to Equal-Life. As a result of these discussions, 66 questions were proposed as possible questions of interest to the project and rated on relevance and testability within the consortium (Benz, 2020). The results of this internal Delphi informed the overarching research questions list of Equal-Life (Annex 9). The 'external' Delphi collected information about the needs that the stakeholders are facing in relation to children's and adolescent mental health and cognitive development. The results of the external Delphi guided the research formulation process by providing insight on what stakeholders advise us to do research on (D8.1).

3.1.2 Co design workshops

Co-design workshops were organised in Skopje (2022) and Helsinki (2023). Co-design is the act of creating interaction with stakeholders (policymakers, end-users) specifically within a design development process to ensure that the results meet their needs and are usable. Its aim is to create something not only for people, but also with them. Stakeholders can become creators of a product being actively involved in the creation process. Co-design is often a transdisciplinary process and the results can be incorporated in guidelines etc. In Equal-Life the co-design was used as a tool to enable stakeholders to use Equal-Life results for policy making or to draft interventions

The task "Co-design workshops with consortium and stakeholders" related to D8.4 had the objective to establish a bi-directional dialogue between the Equal-Life project and (inter)national policy makers to 1) translate project results into effective children health policies and 2) inject knowledge about best practices and health policies into the project. This task ensures that the generated knowledge (on exposome, mechanisms, and health effects) is developed in line with the needs of the broader society, and that knowledge of the involved (public and private) stakeholders will help to interpret the results. This science-policy interaction gives a better understanding of the societal impact and relevance of the Equal-Life research both for the scientists within the project as for the stakeholders. We have identified key stakeholder (policy makers, regulators and research networks), and set up a formal co-design workshop and two stakeholder fora and established regular interaction between scientists and stakeholders.

3.1.3 Stakeholder fora

Stakeholder fora were organised in Ljubljana (2022), Milan (2022) and Como (2023). Stakeholder Forum means a platform open to representatives of institutions, national, regional and local authorities, organised interests and individual entities from different domains, higher education, research, associations, civil society and cluster organisations, as well as other interested parties from across a selected knowledge or policy focus.

For the following project period the next steps are:

New events on stakeholder involvement in the Equal-Life events are planned: 1 last meeting in person in Cork, two webinars/workshops and an end event in 2025 for stakeholders, potentially jointly with ISGlobal and JRC (see page 8)

During these events discussions between stakeholders and researchers are planned to interpret the results, to identify common features of the different models and discuss evidence-based recommendations for (categories of) interventions aiming to improve children's mental health and cognitive development. Even if it turns out that Equal-Life results are explorative only and that is too early to formulate scientific evidence-based recommendations for interventions, this is considered as an important outcome for the discussion with stakeholders. An important feedback during the discussions in the stakeholders' workshops and fora so far in Equal-Life is that such evidence based interventions would be considered by stakeholders as very helpful and useful.

Work on the toolbox and the handbook continues and development of a training protocol.

3.1.4 Conclusions thus far and future plans

Based on the series of events described above it was concluded that stakeholders are primarily interested in the **practical implications** of Equal-Life results. Stakeholders regard the Equal-Life toolbox as a set of tools that helps those interested in the Equal-Life project (at various levels) to explore, understand, and reuse the resulting outcomes. The Equal-Life handbook should accompany the toolbox as a guide for practical use and help conceptualize what is being presented. It should assist the stakeholders to understand the connections between the multiple results displayed and what they mean for options of interventions.

It is in the interest of stakeholders that results provide **options for interventions**. In different countries (and regions, communities) power and finances are on different scales. Therefore, scientific data/results, and recommendations for interventions should be categorized by these scales.

Results and recommendations should be presented in a **language that is understood by stakeholders**. Due to the different languages, goals, motivations, and sense of urgency, the communication between scientists and stakeholders is a complex task. For the scientific community, nearness to decision-makers is important. Scientists should make use of communication experts were applicable in order to communicate their data results and recommendations.

Not only is the communication between scientists and stakeholders an issue. There are different groups of stakeholders with different backgrounds. Interdisciplinarity and **collaboration between stakeholder groups** is essential in regards to effective interventions. The youngsters themselves and their parents should not be forgotten as important stakeholder groups. The research and derived interventions are about their lives.

Stakeholder involvement is not a one-direction communication from the scientific community to stakeholders. Co-design means also learning from and listening to stakeholders and support in defining **key questions to address and the interpretation of findings**.

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4 Development of a Virtual Toolbox

All nine projects that make up the European Human Exposome Network each responded to the call text (Call SC1-BHC-28-2019), which included the development of a toolbox both in the title (“The Human Exposome Project: a toolbox for assessing and addressing the impact of environment on health”) and in the expected impacts (“Enabling researchers and policy makers to continuously include new knowledge in the policy making processes by using the toolbox to generate data and information”).

The nine projects have thus in common that they will develop a toolbox and make this available to researchers and policy makers outside the Projects and beyond the lifespan of the Projects. Toolbox contents are specific to each project, but may include, for example, database and results catalogues, data collection protocols, analysis pipelines and protocols, health impact assessment and intervention toolkits, e-learning tutorials, and policy recommendations.

It is recognised across the Network that it will be important to build an **inventory of tools** developed in all Projects, in order to avoid that stakeholders wishing to find certain tools would have to search nine separate toolboxes.

This tool inventory or “virtual toolbox” will be available on the Network website and will allow users to search through the tools, using an easy-to-use classification of tools. Links to the location of each tool, as well as a brief explanation of its use, will be included.

The development of this virtual toolbox will take place in several steps and will be overseen by the Communication and Dissemination WG:

- in the *launch phase* a list of expected project specific toolboxes items will be assembled, and the Network website will flag the expected contents of the virtual toolbox;
- in the *continuation phase*, a blueprint for the virtual toolbox will be developed, mapping project-specific items to wider toolbox topic areas and developing procedures for its implementation on the website;
- in the *final phase*, the virtual toolbox will be implemented on the Network website.

The development of the virtual toolbox will work closely with other relevant Network working groups, e.g. metadata WG and the statistics WG.

The Equal-Life toolbox

The overall aim of work package 9 is to develop the Equal-Life Toolkit, a “living” software and documental toolkit including innovative approaches, technologies and methods to exploit exposome implementations during the project and to enable generalization and repeatability of the approach in future implementations. The toolkit will comprise a Web-based data and knowledge exploration application, as well as a guidance document suitable to be broadly used and adaptable for new data and methods, and for disseminations of results. The results of the non-targeted and targeted analyses in WP1 and WP7 will constitute the input of the Equal-Life toolkit. The methods as developed in WP6 and the indicators formulated in WP1 and WP4 will provide the methodological and validation guidelines that will be implemented in the software tools and described in the documentation. Therefore, the devised toolkit provides the instrument for a comprehensive understanding of the project results and for supporting future repeatability of the experience, especially for devising possible further health interventions beyond the current project. WP9 has a strong link with the objectives, tasks and deliverables of WP11 (cluster activities).

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Specific objectives are to:

- O9.1. design the tools with inputs from WP1, WP4, WP6, WP7, and WP8, also considering requirements coming from existing tools at regional level;
- O9.2. implement software prototypes for the designed tools;
- O9.3. develop and coordinate the preparation of a Guidance Document
- O9.4. organise training workshops with regional end-users

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5 Overview of dissemination activities (M48)

Equal-Life website: www.equallife.eu

EHEN website: Common reporting on key events and achievements from the nine EHEN projects, through the Network's website and newsletters: Key outputs and events from each project will be posted on the Network's website on a regular basis, in a perspective of providing a global overview of the Network's achievements. The WG Communication will also prepare a newsletter on Network activities which will be distributed at least every 12 months to all Network partners and stakeholders, as further described in section 5. Representatives from each project are responsible for providing the content. The respective WG leaders in each period are responsible for compiling the first draft of this newsletter. The Network newsletter could also directly link to existing news, social media posts from the nine projects.

Social media: The social media use thus far is limited to the linked in site which is primarily used by WP8 and stakeholders .

Publications : listed below

Peer reviewed articles

1. Alatalo, A., de Sousa Maciel, I., Kucháriková, N., Chew, S., van Kamp, I., Foraster, M., Julvez, J. & Kanninen, K. M. (2023). The Interaction between Circulating Cell-Free Mitochondrial DNA and Inflammatory Cytokines in Predicting Human Mental Health Issue Risk in Adolescents: An Explorative Study. *Biomedicines*, 11(3), 818. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines11030818>
2. van Asten, T., Milias, V., Bozzon, A. & Psyllidis, A. (2023). "Eyes on the street": Estimating natural surveillance along Amsterdam city streets using street-level imagery. CUPUM 2023.
3. Botteldooren, D., Van Renterghem, T., Dekoninck, L., Persson Waye, K., Smith, M.A., Lercher, P., Dzhambov, A., Hornikx, M., Terzakis, M.E., Clark, C. & Foraster, M. (2022). Designing a composite indicator for sleep with emphasis on children. Proceedings of the 24th International congress on Acoustics, ICA. Gyeongju, South Korea, oct 24-28.
4. Cai, Y., Hansell, A.L., Granell, R., Blangiardo, M., Zottoli, M., Fecht, D., Gulliver, J., Henderson, A.J. & Elliott, P. (2020). Prenatal, Early-Life, and Childhood Exposure to air pollution and lung function: The ALSPAC Cohort. *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine*, 202(1), 112-123. <https://doi.org/10.1164/rccm.201902-0286OC>.
5. Dzhambov, A.M., Lercher, P., Rüdiger, J., Browning, M.H.E.M. & Markevych, I. (2022) Home gardens and distances to nature associated with behavior problems in alpine schoolchildren: Role of secondhand smoke exposure and biomarkers. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, 243: 113975. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2022.113975>
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- Renterghem, T., Jeram, S., Selander, J., Arat, A., White, K., Julvez, J., Clark, C., Foraster, M. & van Kamp, I. (2023). Protective effect of restorative possibilities on cognitive function and mental health in children and adolescents: A scoping review including the role of physical activity. *Environmental Research*, Volume 233, 116452, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.116452>
7. Dzhambov, A., Lercher, P., Botteldooren, D. (2023). Childhood sound disturbance and sleep problems in Alpine valleys with high levels of traffic exposures and greenspace. *Environmental Research*, volume 242, 117642. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.117642>
 8. Dohmen, M., Braat-Eggen, E., Kemperman, A. & Hornikx, M. (2023). The Effects of Noise on Cognitive Performance and Helplessness in Childhood: A Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(1): 288. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20010288>
 9. Gudi-Mindermann, H., White, M., Roczen, J., Riedel, N., Dreger, S., Bolte, G. (2023). Integrating the social environment with an equity perspective into the exposome paradigm: A new conceptual framework of the Social Exposome. *Environmental Research*, 233, 116485. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.116485>
 10. Heinonen-Guzejev, M., Whipp, A. M., Wang, Z., Ranjit, A., Palviainen, T., van Kamp, I., & Kaprio, J. (2023). Perceived Occupational Noise Exposure and Depression in Young Finnish Adults. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(6), 4850. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20064850>
 11. van Kamp, I., Persson Waye, K., Kanninen, K., Gulliver, J., Bozzon, A., Psyllidis, A., Boshuizen, H., Selander, J., van den Hazel, P., Brambilla, M., Foraster, M., Julvez, J., Klatte, M., Jeram, S., Lercher, P., Botteldooren, D., Ristovska, G., Kaprio, J., Schreckenberg, D., Hornikx, M., Fels, J., Weber, M., Braat-Eggen, E., Hartmann, J., Clark, C., Vrijkotte, T., Brown, L., Bolte, G. & Equal-Life Scientific Team (2022). Early environmental quality and life-course mental health effects: The Equal-Life project. *Environmental Epidemiology*, 6(1), e183. <https://doi.org/10.1097/EE9.000000000000183>
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 13. Martínez-Vilavella, G., Pujol, J., Blanco-Hinojo, L., Deus, J., Rivas, I., Persavento, C., Sunyer, J., Foraster, M. (2023). The effects of exposure to road traffic noise at school on central auditory pathway functional connectivity. *Environmental Research*, 226, 115574. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.115574>
 14. Miliás, V., & Psyllidis, A. (2021). Assessing the influence of point-of-interest features on the classification of place categories. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 86, 101597. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2021.101597>
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Conference papers

Year	Author(s)	Title	Conference	Url
2021	Maud Dohmen , Ella Braat-Eggen , Astrid Kemperman , Maarten Hornikx	A new approach for measuring space-time-activity-exposure patterns of children	13th ICBEN Congress on Noise as a Public Health Problem. 15-18 June 2022	Link
2021	Loh, K., & Fels, J.	A concept to evaluate activity-based acoustic settings in primary schools appropriate for children's hearing	13th ICBEN Congress on Noise as a Public Health Problem, Stockholm, Sweden	
2022	Dick Botteldooren, Timothy Van Renterghem, Luc Dekoninck, Kerstin Persson Waye, Michael Smith, Peter Lercher, Angel Dzhambov, Maarten Hornikx, Michail Evangelos Terzakis, Charlotte Clark and Maria Foraster	Designing a composite indicator for sleep with emphasis on children	Proceedings of ICA, 24-27 October 2022, Gyeongju, South Korea	
2022	Schreckenberg, D., Kuhlmann, J., Belke, C. & Benz, S.L.	Reflections about the assessment of short-term noise annoyance	Proceedings of ICA, 24-27 October 2022, Gyeongju, South Korea	Link
2022	Katja Kanninen	mental health biomarker work	EHEN meeting 2022	
2022	Yingxin Chen, Yutong Cai, John Gulliver, Charlotte Clark, Anna Hansell	Prenatal, early-life, and childhood exposure to source-specific air pollution and behavioural problems in the ALSPAC cohort	34th Annual Conference of the International Society for Environmental Epidemiology, 8-21 September 2022	
2022	Timothy Van Renterghem , Wout Van Hauwermeiren, Valentin Le Bescond, Luc Dekoninck, Dick Botteldooren	Urban advanced noise indicator mapping relying on street categorization and measurements	Proceedings of Internoise 2022.	
2022	Loh, K., & Fels, J.	Challenges and methods to design a dual-task experiment in spatial auditory environments for young children aged three to six years old	Fortschritte Der Akustik - DAGA 2022. DAGA 2022, Stuttgart, Germany	
2022	Jansen, S., White, M.	Social inequalities in the Exposome and achieving equity; What are we thinking about in Equal-Life?	EHEN WG on Ethics & Legal Issues, September 2021.	
2022	White, M.	Equity considerations in interventions within Equal-Life: development of a logic model framework for assessing the equity impacts of urban interventions	EHEN meeting 2022	
2022	Roos Teeuwen	Measuring urban greenspace accessibility from mobile settings	EHEN meeting 2022	

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2022	Vasileios Milias	Co-accessibility of public spaces: towards age-inclusive and accessible public spaces	EHEN meeting 2022
2022	Spilski, J., Giehl, C., Boshuizen, H., Wong, A., Bergström, K., Lachmann, T., & Klatte, M.	Traffic noise and children's health: New insights from a machine learning algorithm?	Proceedings of the Inter-Noise 2022. Glasgow, Scotland.
2022	Spilski, J., Koole R., Giehl, C., Boshuizen, H., Bergström, K., Lachmann, T., & Klatte, M.	The relevance of the number of aircraft events for children's cognition: Further evidence from a machine learning algorithm	Proceedings of the 24th International Congress on Acoustics (ICA) Link
2022	Sanne Meijering, Elise van Kempen, Rik Bogers, Jurriaan Hoekstra, Tanja Vrijkotte, Jolanda Boer, Anneke Blokstra, Roel Vermeulen, Ulrike Gehring, Judith Vonk, Irene van Kamp, Albert Wong, Hendrik Boshuizen	Variable importance: A data-driven search for exposome features that affect child development.	EHEN meeting 2022
2022	Benz, S., Schreckenber, D., van den Hazel, P., Weber, M., Jansen, S., Ristovska, G., Arat, A., White, M., Spiroski, I., van Kamp, I.	Involving stakeholders in noise research projects: Towards a holistic approach for interaction between scientific and practical considerations	Proceedings of the 24th International Congress on Acoustics (ICA) Link
2022	Benz, S., Weber, M., van den Hazel, P., Jansen, S., Arat, A., White, M., Riedel, N., Ristovska, G., van Kamp, I., Schreckenber, D.	Comparing perspectives on research needs from stakeholders vs. researchers in an exposome project.	European Public Health Conference
2022	Gordana Ristovska et al.	Stakeholders involvement in identification of research and policy needs for children's environment and mental health.	European Public Health conference
2022	Gordana Ristovska et al.	Connecting science with policy through stakeholder's involvement for better mental health of children.	EHEN meeting 2022
2022	Sandionigi A, Weber M, Benz S, Ristovska G, Jeram S, Schreckenber D, van den Hazel P, Brambilla M, Balduini M.	Moving from exposome science to intervention practice: digital toolbox creation to support activities in the field of children's mental health and cognitive development	EHEN meeting 2022
2022	van den Hazel P, Ristovska G, Weber M, Sandionigi A, Benz S.	A Holistic Approach to Urban and Children's Mental Health.	EPH November 2022
2022	Sammie Jansen	Human Exposome Ethical considerations	4TU Ethics bi-annual conference on Ethics and Technolog

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2022	Sammie Jansen	Ethics of Early Detection of Health Determinants to Predict Health Outcomes: Relevance for the Human Exposome	16th World Congress of Bioethics on July 22 in Basel Switzerland
2023	Loh, K., Seitz, J., Braren, H., & Fels, J.	Speech Transmission Index Measured using Adult and Children Head and Torso Simulators	Proceeding of Forum Acusticum 2023. Forum Acusticum 2023, Torino, Italy Link
2023	Loh, K., Seitz, J., Rust, F., & Fels, J.	A concept to evaluate activity-based acoustic settings in preschools for children aged three to six	Proceedings of Inter-Noise 2023. Inter-noise 2023, Chiba, Japan
2023	Seitz, J., & Loh, K.	A Listening Experiment to Study Intentional Switching of Auditory Selective Attention in Preschool Children	International Student Conference on Electrical Engineering, Prague, Czech Republic.
2023	Seitz, J., Loh, K., & Fels, J.	Design of a child-appropriate dual-task paradigm examining the influence of different noise conditions on listening effort in adults	Proceeding of Forum Acusticum 2023. Forum Acusticum 2023, Torino, Italy. Link
2023	Seitz, J., Loh, K., Nolden, S., & Fels, J.	Investigating Intentional Switching of Spatial Auditory Selective Attention in an Experiment with Preschool children	Fortschritte Der Akustik - DAGA 2023. DAGA 2023, Hamburg, Germany
2023	Julvez, J.	a nutritional intervention and cognitive function in behalf of Equal-Life	EHEN meeting 2023
2023	Smith, M. G., Wiberg, A., Lindgren, S., Simonovic, D., Vincens, N., Kessel, B., Chen, Y., Botteldooren, D., Dekoninck, L., Friberg, P and Persson Waye, K.	A field investigation on associations between environmental noise and adolescent sleep: An Equal-Life study	14 th IC BEN Congress on Noise as a Public Health Problem: 18-22 June 2023 Link
2023	Persson Waye, K., Wiberg, A., Vincens, N., Löve, J., Chen, Y., Holmqvist Gattario, K., Lercher, P., Dzhambov, A. M., Kessel, B., Botteldooren, D., Dekoninck, L., Friberg, P and Smith, M. G.	Exploring the linkage of noise and mental health among adolescents – An Equal-Life study	14 th IC BEN Congress on Noise as a Public Health Problem: 18-22 June 2023 Link
2023	Vasileios Miliias, Alessandro Bozzon, Achilleas Psyllidis	Is it safe to be attractive? Disentangling the influence of streetscape features on the perceived safety and attractiveness of city streets	26 th AGILE Conference on Geographic Information Science, 2023 Link
2023	Vasileios Miliias, Alessandro Bozzon, Achilleas Psyllidis.	Eyes on the street: Estimating natural surveillance along Amsterdam city streets using street-level imagery	Intelligence for Future Cities: Planning through Big Data and Urban Analytics Link

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2023	Roos Teeuwen, Achilleas Psyllidis	Easy as child's play? Co-designing a network-based metric for children's access to play space	18 th International Conference on Computational Urban Planning and Urban Management, CUPUM 2023	Link
2023	Sonja Jeram, Nataša Frigelj, Marcel Kralj, Gordana Ristovska, Urban Bolka, Maja Škafar, Jenny Ahrens, Gabriele Bolte, Maddie White	Implementation of the Environmental Noise Directive 2002/49/EC in Slovenia seen through an equity lens	14 th ICBEN Congress on Noise as a Public Health Problem: 18-22 June 2023	Link
2023	Belke, C., Benz, S., Kuhlmann, J., Leist, L., Klatte, M., Schreckenberger, D.	Walking interviews as a qualitative method of assessing environmental noise perception of preschool children	14 th ICBEN Congress on Noise as a Public Health Problem: 18-22 June 2023	Link
2023	Benz, S., Kuhlmann, J., Van den Hazel, P., Weber, M., Jeram, S., Sandionigi, A., Jansen, S., Ristovska, G., White, M., Psyllidis, A., Teeuwen, R., Ahrens, J., Schreckenberger, D.	Stakeholder involvement in research on health impact of environmental exposure	14 th ICBEN Congress on Noise as a Public Health Problem: 18-22 June 2023	Link
2023	Kuhlmann, J., Benz, S., Sandionigi, A., Jeram, S., Jansen, S., Van den Hazel, P., Weber, M., Ristovska, G., White, M., Schreckenberger, D	Stakeholders' views about the environmental noise impact on children's and adolescents' health and cognitive development	14 th ICBEN Congress on Noise as a Public Health Problem: 18-22 June 2023	Link
2023	Maud Dohmen , Ella Braat-Eggen , Astrid Kemperman , Maarten Hornikx	A laboratory experiment exploring the effect of chronic- and background noise on cognitive performance and motivation	14 th ICBEN Congress on Noise as a Public Health Problem: 18-22 June 2023	Link
2023	Klatte, M.; Leist, L.; Bergström, K.; Belke, C. Schreckenberger, D.; Konerding, M. & Lachmann, T.	Speech-in-noise perception and phonological awareness in preschool children	Conference of the Developmental Psychology Group of the German Psychological Society (DGPs), September 2023, Berlin.	
2023	Gabin Drouard	Linking adolescent BMI trajectories to the proteome reveals the complexity of the internal exposome: a multi-omics longitudinal twin study	consortium meeting	
2023	Gabin Drouard	Longitudinal multi-omics study reveals common etiology underlying association between plasma proteome and BMI trajectories in adolescent and young adult twins	EMBL Nording Partnership meeting, Helsinki, 13-15 September	

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2023	M Heinonen-Guzejev, A M Whipp, Z Wang, A Ranjit, T Palviainen, I van Kamp, J Kaprio	The association of depressive symptoms with perceived occupational noise exposure in young adults.	16th European Public Health Conference 2023, Dublin, Ireland, 8-11 November 2023.
2023	Zhiyang Wang	oral presentation	EHEN meeting 2023 page 887 - 35th Annual Conference of the International Society for Environmental Epidemiology, Kaohsiung, 2023 Link
2023	Zhiyang Wang	Systematic evaluation of the environmental effect on depressive symptoms: exposome-wide association study and twin modeling	14th ICBEN Congress on Noise as a Public Health Problem. 18-22.6.2023 Link
2023	Botteldooren, D., Van Renterghem, T., Can, A., Dzhambov, A. M., & Lercher, P.	Noise indicators for sleep disturbance and how to model them.	

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Dissemination & Communication activities

Activity	Dissemination & Communication activity category	Attended/organized by
Presentation of Equal-life in ISGlobal Retreat, Barcelona, Spain.	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	ISGlobal
Press release Gothenburg University EU grant	Press release	UGOT
Information meeting at the School of Public Health and Community Medicine	Oral presentations at the School of public Health and Community Medicine	UGOT
LinkedIn account	Social Media	INCHES
Presentation of Equal-life in Childhood and Environment Seminars, ISGlobal, Barcelona, Spain	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	ISGlobal
ISGlobal 1st Exposome HUB meeting, presentation of Equal-life, Barcelona, Spain.	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	ISGlobal
Formerly Twitter account @EquallifeEU	Social Media	RIVM
Network Advisory Board meeting 2020	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	RIVM
Kick off meeting press release	Press release	RIVM
Contributing text about WP4 Social Exposome to the Equal Life website (https://www.equal-life.eu/en/node/341)	Website	UB
Press release: launch of Equal-Life website and project https://www.public-health.uni-bremen.de/aktuelles/?print=1&newsdetail=535	Press release	UB
Overview of the Equal-Life project and UB's participation on the UB Institute of Public Health and Nursing Research page (https://www.ipp.uni-bremen.de/abteilungen/sozialepidemiologie/projekte/?proj=815)	Website	UB

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Presentation about the Equal-Life project and the role of UB within the consortium to the expert advisory group (Environment) of the German National Cohort study	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UB
Article titled ‚Equal-Life: Early environmental quality and life-course mental health effects‘ giving project overview in the University of Bremen’s IPP-Info 17 („Sociological perspectives for public health‘, issued Fall 2020). (https://www.public-health.uni-bremen.de/uploads/IPPInfo/IPP-Info_Ausgabe-17_RZ_WEB_Links_v2.pdf)	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	UB
Presentation to the Department of Social Epidemiology at UB about Equal-Life and WP work, and UB involvement	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UB
Presentation to the Department of Social Epidemiology at UB and workshop on scoping review methodology in place for Deliverable 4.1 (Conceptual framework of the Social Exposome)	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UB
Presentation to the Department of Social Epidemiology at UB about the draft preliminary conceptual framework of the Social Exposome	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UB
Presentation of the project at Sound Environment and Health webpage	Website	UGOT
Gordana Ristovska, Peter van den Hazel, Miriam Weber, Sammie Jansen, Sarah Benz, Maddie White, Arzu Arat, Igor Spiroski, Dirk Schreckenber, Irene van Kamp. Stakeholders’ involvement in identification of research and policy needs for children’s mental health. EPH 2021 (online) Oral presentation	Participation to a Conference	IJZRM
Sammie Jansen - 4TU Ethics bi-annual conference on Ethics and Technology attended by Sammie Jansen, poster presented: Human Exposome Ethical considerations	Participation to a Conference	RIVM
Conference contribution	Participation to a Conference	RWTH

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Maud Dohmen - Guest lecture given online for the University of Bremen (Bremen, Germany). Lecturer: Maud Dohmen. Topic: Health effects of environmental noise and the application of time-activity-exposure patterns.	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	TUE
Maud Dohmen Guest lecture given online for ICAHN school of medicine (environmental public health) (New York, USA). Lecturer: Maud Dohmen. Topic: Environmental Noise and Children's Mental Health and Cognition, the application of the exposome concept.	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	TUE
Maud Dohmen - information video recruitment in-depth research	Video/Film	TUE
White, M., Jansen, S. (2021). Social inequalities in the Exposome and achieving equity. What are we thinking about in Equal-Life? EHEN Group on Ethics and legal issues, September 2021, International digital meeting.	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	UB
Article titled <i>'The Social Exposome: concept development and participatory research process in Equal-Life'</i> in the University of Bremen's IPP-Info 18 (,Participation in research and care', issued Fall 2021). (https://www.public-health.uni-bremen.de/uploads/IPPInfo/IPP-Info_Ausgabe-18_web_220310.pdf) Roczen, J., White, M., Gudi-Mindermann, H., Bolte, G. (2021). Das Soziale Exposom: Konzeptentwicklung und partizipativer Forschungsprozess in Equal-Life. IPP Info 18 – Schwerpunktthema: Partizipation in der Forschung und in der Versorgung. Newsletter des IPP, 18, pp. 21-22.	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	UB
Roczen, J., White, M., Gudi-Mindermann, H. (2021). Structure of the Equal-Life project and the operationalization of the Social Exposome. Internal presentation at the regular Social epidemiology team meeting. October 2021, Digital meeting at the University of Bremen, Germany.	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UB

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Presentation to the Department of Social Epidemiology at UB about the final preliminary conceptual framework of the Social Exposome	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UB
Updating text about the Social Exposome work package (WP4) to the Equal Life website (https://www.equal-life.eu/en/node/341)	Website	UB
Presentation about Equal-Life and the Social Exposome at the EHEN Network Day (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=b5DBXJVSec)	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	UB
Meeting with researcher from EHEN Project EXPANSE to discuss overlapping work on assessing intervention effects in WP4	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	UB
Helping with co-ordination (contacting/organising speakers) of EHEN Conference breakout session on the Social Exposome. Presentation as part of Breakout Session on the Social Exposome and Social Inequalities in the Exposome (https://ehen.sites.uu.nl/break-out-sessions/the-social-exposome-and-social-inequalities-in-the-exposome/).	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	UB
Article titled 'The Social Exposome: Concept Development and Participatory Research Process in Equal-Life' giving update about establishment of conceptual framework the Social Exposome and stakeholder involvement and participation in the Equal-Life project in the UB IPP-Info 18 ('Participation in care and research (including participatory assessment of health services)'). In Press.	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	UB
University of Bremen's IPP-Info 18 Participation in research and care, not peer-reviewed article	Other	UB
Project presentation to Neuro-Innovation Cofund PhD program	Pitch Event	UEF
Presentation of the importance of a life course perspective	Urban sound symposium 2021	UGOT
Marja Heinonen-Guzejev. Noise Sensitivity and Health Effects of Environmental Noise.	Participation to a Conference	UH

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Global Conference on Noise & Health, Deafness. 11-12 December 2021. Trivandrum (presentation online).		
Yingxin Chen, Yutong Cai, John Gulliver, Charlotte Clark, Anna Hansell. Prenatal, early-life, and childhood exposure to source-specific air pollution and behavioural problems in the ALSPAC cohort. 34th Annual Conference of the International Society for Environmental Epidemiology, 8-21 September 2022.	Participation to a Conference	ULEIC
Participation to a Workshop	UH	
Miriam Weber: a workshop has been organised by Utrecht during the Nordic Public Health Conference (June 2022)	Organisation of a Workshop	CoU
NPHC workshop, title "Co-designing policies, settings and tools for children's mental health and cognitive development: professionals and researchers invited!"	Organisation of a Workshop	CoU
Urban Transitions 2022 conference, poster, title "Human exposome: a new perspective on urban planning for children's health?"	Participation to a Conference	CoU
Utrecht presented Equal-Life and specifically the tasks concerning stakeholder involvement and policy-science interface (WP8) during the EuroCities working group noise meeting (April 20220), during the WHO European Healthy Cities Network's Environment and Health Working Group meetings (various meetings in 2021 and 2022) and during the Urban Transitions 2022 conference (November 2022).	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	CoU
Dzhambov A, Lercher P, Rüdiger J. Noise in restorative environments – Perceptions, positive and negative environmental components in Tyrolean children. 51st International Congress and Exposition on Noise Control Engineering 2022, INTER-NOISE 2022, Glasgow,UK	Participation to a Conference	GUT
Jordi Julvez: Press Release. "Studying the exposome for a healthier future for all children". 21-02-2022. https://goherohealth.com/childrens-	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	IISPV

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health/studying-the-exposome-for-a-healthier-future-for-all-children/		
Gordana Ristovska, Peter van den Hazel, Miriam Weber, Sammie Jansen, Sarah Benz, Maddie White, Arzu Arat, Igor Spiroski, Dirk Schreckenber, Irene van Kamp. Connecting science with policy through stakeholder's involvement for better mental health of children. EHEN 2022	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	IJZRM
Gordana Ristovska, Peter van den Hazel, Miriam Weber, Sammie Jansen, Sarah Benz, Maddie White, Mihail Kocubovski, Igor Spiroski, Anna Sandionigi, Dirk Schreckenber, Irene van Kamp. INFLUENCE OF EXPOSOME ON MENTAL HEALTH AND COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN – SURVEY WITH THE STAKEHOLDERS. GREDIT 2022	Participation to a Conference	IJZRM
Participation in break-out session EHEN conference	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	INCHES
van den Hazel P, Ristovska G, Weber M, Sandionigi A, Benz S. A Holistic Approach to Urban and Children's Mental Health. EPH November 2022	Participation to a Conference	INCHES
ISGlobal GIS team. Urban exposome: calculation of green spaces with Google Earth Engine, ISGlobal exposome Hub meeting, May 26, 2022	Organisation of a Workshop	ISGlobal
Participation KI team: Jenny, Arzu, Johanna (no presentations)	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	KI
Sandionigi A, Weber M, Benz S, Ristovska G, Jeram S, Schreckenber D, van den Hazel P, Brambilla M, Balduini M. Moving from exposome science to intervention practice: digital toolbox creation to support activities in the field of children's mental health and cognitive development. Barcelona 24-25 May 2022- EHEN Scientific Meeting - Oral presentation	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	QUA
Stakeholder Module (stakeholder-equal-life.eu). van den Hazel P, Sandionigi A, Weber M, Balduini M, Irene van Kamp, Kim van Wijk,	Website	QUA

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Schreckenber D, Benz S, Ristovska G, Jeram S, , Brambilla M.		
Organization EHEN conference Barcelona	Organisation of a Conference	RIVM
Sanne Meijering presented her PhD work “Variable importance: A data-driven search for exposome features that affect child development” at the European Human Exposome Network's annual Scientific Meeting in May 2022	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	RIVM
Irene van Kamp presented the Equal-life highlights at the European Human Exposome Network's annual Scientific Meeting in May 2022	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	RIVM
Irene van Kamp co-chaired the welcome plenary sessions and took part of a panel discussion during the European Human Exposome Network's annual Scientific Meeting May 24 and 25 2022	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	RIVM
Irene van Kamp participated in a panel discussion during the European Human Exposome Network's annual Scientific Meeting in May 2022	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	RIVM
Sammie Jansen - European Human Exposome Network's annual Scientific Meeting - presented PhD work for the EHEN working group Ethics and Law: “Ethics of early detection of health determinants & prediction of health outcomes”	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	RIVM
RIVM has introduced Equal-Life during the ICA in South-Korea (October 24-28, 2022)	Participation to a Conference	RIVM
Irene van Kamp and the Equal-Life Team Early environmental quality and life-course mental health effects: The Equal-Life project ICA, 2022, Gyeongju, Zuid Korea Proceedings paper 0016	Other	RIVM
RIVM was theme organiser of the noise and health sessions at internoise including some Equal-Life work. Internoise conference in Glasgow (21-24 August 2022)	Organisation of a Workshop	RIVM
Stakeholder forum Milan 2022 and Italian stakeholder focus group	Organisation of a Workshop	RIVM

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WP7 Talk by Elise: Dissemination to stakeholders were made during 16 November 2022, Milan	Participation to a Workshop	RIVM
Open Access Article: 'Studying the exposome concept for a healthier future for all children': https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/studying-the-exposome-concept-for-a-healthier-future-for-all-children/136663/	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	RIVM
Open Access Article 'Interviews with PhDs': https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/article/equal-life-team-improving-child-exposome-and-quality-of-life/145820/	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	RIVM
Sammie Jansen - short essay on ethics of exposome for wider audience, published in Dutch bioethics journal https://nvbioethiek.files.wordpress.com/2022/05/podium-21-4-digitaal.pdf	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	RIVM
Sammie Jansen - blog for the 4TU Centre for Ethics and Technology on 'The power of the human exposome' https://ethicsandtechnology.eu/blog-post/the-power-of-the-human-exposome/	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	RIVM
Equal-Life was presented at the 16th World Congress of Bioethics on July 22 in Basel Switzerland, where Sammie Jansen presented her PhD work. "Ethics of Early Detection of Health Determinants to Predict Health Outcomes: Relevance for the Human Exposome"	Participation to a Conference	RIVM
Sammie Jansen - attendance International Conference Ethics of Socially Disruptive Technologies `+ organized and moderated a panel discussion 'At the intersection of Ethics and STEM', Oegstgeest, Netherlands	Participation to a Conference	RIVM
Giehl, C. (2022). Mediation models in SEM. Presented as an Introduction at the mediation model Hackathon organized by the RIVM in June, 2022, Netherlands.	Training	RIVM
Animation introduction Project Equal-Life. https://www.equal-life.eu/ Translations of subtitles were provided in all languages of	Video/Film	RIVM

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the countries participating in the in-depth studies (NL, ES, CAT, FI, IT, DE, SE)		
Loh, K., & Fels, J. (2022). Challenges and methods to design a dual-task experiment in spatial auditory environments for young children aged three to six years old. <i>Fortschritte Der Akustik - DAGA 2022</i> . DAGA 2022, Stuttgart, Germany.	Participation to a Conference	RWTH
Loh, K., Hoog Antink, C., Nolden, S., & Fels, J. (2021). Combined assessment of cognitive and physiological parameters in child-appropriate listening experiments. [Invited talk] Euronoise 2021, e-congress, Madeira, Portugal.	Participation to a Conference	RWTH
Loh, K., & Fels, J. (2021). A concept to evaluate activity-based acoustic settings in primary schools appropriate for children's hearing. [Invited talk] 13th IC BEN Congress on Noise as a Public Health Problem, Stockholm, Sweden.	Participation to a Conference	RWTH
Fels, J., & Loh, K. (2022, January 21st). Challenges and methods to design a child-appropriate speech-in-noise experiment in spatial auditory environments for young children [Invited talk]. SPIN 2022, Virtual meeting.	Participation to a Conference	RWTH
Roos Teeuwen: Presentation at the 2022 EHEN Conference "Measuring urban greenspace accessibility from mobile settings". Barcelona, May 24, 2022.	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	TUD
Vasileios Milias: Presentation at the 2022 EHEN Conference "Co-accessibility of public spaces: towards age-inclusive and accessible public spaces". Barcelona, May 25, 2022	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	TUD
Roos Teeuwen: Workshop "Evaluating children's access to public outdoor play space". Milan,	Organisation of a Workshop	TUD
Achilleas Psyllidis: Presentation "New methodological approaches to measuring the physical environment". Equal-Life Stakeholder Forum, Milan	Participation to a Workshop	TUD

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Vasileios Milias: Presentation "From POIs to accessibility and beyond". Geospatial Brownbag session, HERE Technologies (online)	Participation to a Conference	TUD
Achilleas Psyllidis: https://youtu.be/co3q_DAEt1E	Video/Film	TUD
Youtube video: Designing with Location Intelligence: Urban health and well-being	Video/Film	TUD
Stakeholder forum Milan 2022 presentation	Participation to a Workshop	TUE
Maud Dohmen - presentation at networking event	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	TUE
Maud Dohmen - website for in-depth research participants	Website	TUE
JS presented further results of Random Forest Analysis on the ICA Conference, October 2022, Gyeongju Korea	Participation to a Conference	TUK
Spilski, J., Koole R., Giehl, C., Boshuizen, H., Bergström, K., Lachmann, T., & Klätte, M. (2022). The relevance of the number of aircraft events for children's cognition: Further evidence from a machine learning algorithm. Proceedings of the 24th International Congress on Acoustics (ICA) 2022. Gyeongju, Korea https://www.researchgate.net/publication/362929624_Traffic_noise_and_children's_health_New_insights_from_a_machine_learning_algorithm	Other	TUK
Jan Spilski presented results of Random-Forest-Analysis on the Inter-Noise Conference, August 2022, Glasgow (Scotland)	Participation to a Conference	TUK
Spilski, J., Giehl, C., Boshuizen, H., Wong, A., Bergström, K., Lachmann, T., & Klätte, M. (2022). Traffic noise and children's health: New insights from a machine learning algorithm? Proceedings of the Inter-Noise 2022. Glasgow, Scotland. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/364959077_The_relevance_of_the_number_of_aircraft_events_for_children's_cognition	Other	TUK

Further_evidence_from_a_machine_learning_algorithm		
Maria Klatte presented the preschool study on the stakeholder forum, November 2022, Milano (Italy)	Participation to a Workshop	TUK
Giehl, C., Boshuizen, H., & Meijering, S. (2022). WP6 Overview. Causal path modeling in Equal-Life. What has been done and what will be done. Equal-Life Stakeholder Forum, November 2022, Milan, Italy.	Participation to a Workshop	TUK
White, M., Gudi-Mindermann, H., Roczen, J., Jeram, S., van Kamp, I., & Bolte, G. (2022). Equity considerations in interventions within Equal-Life: Development of a logic model framework for assessing the equity impacts of urban interventions. European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) Scientific meeting, May 2022, Barcelona, Spain	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	UB
Gudi-Mindermann, H., White, M. Ahrens, J., & Bolte, G. (2022). Social Exposome – Concept, application fields, implications. <i>Equal-Life Stakeholder Forum</i> , November 2022, Milan, Italy.	Participation to a Workshop	UB
Ahrens, J., White, M. (2022). Assessment of social inequities in urban planning interventions. <i>Equal-Life Stakeholder Forum</i> , November 2022, Milan, Italy.	Participation to a Workshop	UB
White, M. (2022). Equity considerations in interventions within Equal-Life: Evaluation with Stakeholders of a logic model framework for assessing the equity impacts of urban interventions. <i>Equal-Life Stakeholder Forum</i> , October 2022, Skopje, North Macedonia.	Participation to a Workshop	UB
Roczen, J., (2022). Equal-Life and the Social Exposome. Meeting between the Institute for Public Health and Nursing Research (IPP) with the Scientific advisory board, February 2022, Digital meeting at the University of Bremen, Germany.	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UB
Presentation Katja Kanninen Barcelona scientific meeting EHEN	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	UEF

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Dissemination of Equal-Life project on August 28, 2022, to the Faculty of Health Sciences at UEF at a research symposium	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UEF
Dissemination of Equal-Life project to high school students on Nov 10, 2022. Attended by PhD student Aino-Kaisa Piironen. Approximately 15 students attended.	Training	UEF
Botteldooren D et al. Designing a composite indicator for sleep with emphasis on children 24th International Congress on Acoustics, ICA 2022, Gyeongju, Korea	Participation to a Conference	Ugent
Dick Botteldooren, Timothy Van Renterghem, Luc Dekoninck, Kerstin Persson Waye, Michael Smith, Peter Lercher, Angel Dzhambov, Maarten Hornikx, Michail Evangelos Terzakis, Charlotte Clark and Maria Foraster, "Designing a composite indicator for sleep with emphasis on children", proceedings of ICA 2022.	Other	UGent
Urban advanced noise indicator mapping relying on street categorization and measurements, T. Van Renterghem, W. Van Hauwermeiren, V. Le Bescond, L. Dekoninck, D. Botteldooren; Proceedings of the 51st international congress and exposition on noise control engineering (Internoise 2022), Glasgow, UK. http://hdl.handle.net/1854/LU-01GSD71C0ZXSV0YCHZNF1QPD5X	Other	Ugent
Natalia Vincens. Exposome, mental health and cognitive development among children and adolescents: conceptual and path models on potential mediators in Equal-Life. Presentation at EHEN SCIENTIFIC MEETING 24 – 25 MAY 2022 BARCELONA	Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)	UGOT
Kerstin Persson Waye. Linking the exposome to mental health and cognitive development among children and adolescents - Conceptual and path models on potential mediators in Equal-Life. Presentation at Milan meeting Nov 2022	Participation to a Workshop	UGOT
Kaprio J: Data Science and Population Health, presentation at the. Institute for Molecular	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UH

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Medicine FIMM retreat June 2, 2022, Helsinki, Finland		
Whipp, AM. "Branched chain amino acids: biomarkers of depression". Presented as an oral presentation during a visit of Prof Anthony J Bull and his students from the Department of Human Biology and Kinesiology at Colorado College, 4 May 2022, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland.	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UH
Wang Z. "Exposome and childhood and adolescence mental health". Presented as an oral presentation with Prof. Tuuli Toivonen and her students from the Department of Geosciences and Geography at the University of Helsinki, 18 Dec. 2022, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UH
Whipp, AM. "Improving diversity in medical research". Invited speaker at Science Day (KLTO and FiNDOS), 2 December 2022, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UH
Invited speaker at Science Day themed "Diversity in clinical research" (KLTO and FiNDOS), 2 December 2022, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland.	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UH
Benz, S., Weber, M., van den Hazel, P., Jansen, S., Arat, A., White, M., Riedel, N., Ristovska, G., van Kamp, I., Schreckenberg, D. (2022). Comparing perspectives on research needs from stakeholders vs. researchers in an exposome project. European Public Health Conference 2022, Berlin: Poster about comparison of results from the stakeholder Delphi survey and the Delphi survey within the project consortium	Participation to a Conference	ZEUS
Benz, S., Schreckenberg, D., van den Hazel, P., Weber, M., Jansen, S., Ristovska, G., Arat, A., White, M., Spirsoiki, I., van Kamp, I. (2022). Involving stakeholders in noise research projects: Towards a holistic approach for interaction between scientific and practical considerations. Proceedings of the International Congress on Acoustics (ICA), 2022, Geyongju, South Korea.	Other	ZEUS

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(https://www.ica2022korea.org/sub_proceedings.php)		
Schreckenber, D., Kuhlmann, J., Belke, C. & Benz, S.L. (2022). Reflections about the assessment of short-term noise annoyance. Proceedings of ICA, 24-27 October 2022, Gyeongju, South Korea. Paper No. ABS-0347. URL: https://www.ica2022korea.org/data/Proceedings_A08.pdf	Other	ZEUS
Lecture at the Genetics Seminar, Norwegian Institute of Public Health, Oslo, Norway June 9, 2023	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UH
Lecture at the 1st annual meeting of twins and multiples, Finnish Multiple Births Organization, Seinäjoki 26. August, 2023	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UH
Online lecture for the course Analysis of Twin Data in Health Science, University of Southern Denmark, October 4, 2023	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	UH
Nat. Mental Health 1, 532–533 research briefing	Press release	UH
Peter vd Hazel - moderation LinkedIn group stakeholders	Social Media	INCHES
Equal-Life PMO team - Twitter account informing the general public of main project outcomes	Social Media	RIVM
Equal-Life PMO team - Equal-Life website	Website	RIVM
Keynote: Irene van Kamp at the Healthy Buildings conference 2023 in Aachen. Title: The exposome and child mental health and cognitive development: methodological challenges	Participation to a conference	RIVM
Presentations Irene van Kamp workshop JRC Depression expert group (April 2023). Title: Early Environmental Quality and Life-course Mental Health Effects Part of the EU-Humane Exposome Project	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	RIVM

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Public domain reach outs

Studying the exposome concept for a healthier future for all children
<https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/studying-the-exposome-concept-for-a-healthier-future-for-all-children/136663/> <https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/studying-the-exposome-concept-for-a-healthier-future-for-all-children/136663/>

Giehl, C., Jansen, S., Milias, V., & Teeuwen, R. (2022). Equal-Life team: Improving child exposome and quality of life. Open Access Government, October 14, 2022, pp. 188—190.
<https://doi.org/10.56367/OAG-036-10295><https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/article/equal-life-team-improving-child-exposome-and-quality-of-life/145820/>

Animation film aimed at children and stakeholders, which was made available on the website: www.equal-life.eu/en. The subtitles were translated to 7 languages (Dutch, German, Spanish, Catalan, Italian, Swedish, Finnish www.equal-life.eu/en)

Webinars: Planned in 2024

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